

ISSUES OF ORGANIZING AND CONDUCTING INVENTORY OF PRODUCTION RESOURCES

M.A.Abduganiev

TSUE " Finance and accounting

Faculty of Accounts student

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Annotation

This article examines the issues of organizing and carrying out inventory of production stocks in enterprises. In particular, issues of formalization of deficits or shortages identified as a result of inventory and reflection in accounting are described.

Key words : production stocks, inventory, surplus, deficit, accounting.

The reliability and accuracy of financial information provided in the annual financial report of economic entities is of great importance. In the structure of assets of enterprises engaged in production activities, production reserves have a large weight. Therefore, it is important to ensure that the information related to the company's production reserves are correctly and clearly reflected in the financial statements. In order to ensure that the information related to production reserves is correctly and accurately reflected in the financial report, it is necessary to carry out an inventory of production reserves before preparing the annual financial report, and the results of the inventory must be formalized in the appropriate order and reflected in the accounting.

The main part.

The accuracy of accounting and reporting information of enterprises is confirmed by inventorying their production stocks. Inventory of production stocks is regulated by BHMS No. 19 entitled "Organization and Transfer of Inventory" and BHMS No. 4 entitled "Inventories".

The issues of reflecting the deficits and excesses identified as a result of the inventory in accounting are approved by the decisions of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Tax Committee, the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population dated March 10, 2004 No. 37, 2004-26, 20/1 "Identified during the inventory regulated by the requirements of the regulation on the procedure for reflecting deficits and surpluses in accounting" (new version).

The main purpose of the inventory is to determine whether production stocks are actually available in terms of kind and value. As a result of the inventory, the correct storage and distribution of assets, the condition of scales and measuring instruments, the accounting procedure, etc. are checked.

is carried out at least once a year before the preparation of financial statements, but after October 1 of the reporting year . In addition, in order to control the maintenance of production stocks, their storage conditions and the state of accounting in the warehouse, regular inspections and selective inventory of materials should be carried out in the period between inventories.

In the following cases, the inventory must be carried out ahead of time:

- lease, purchase, sale of enterprise property, as well as when the enterprise is being reorganized;
- when goods are revalued;
- when the financially responsible person changes;
- when the facts related to looting or abuse, as well as destruction of wealth, are revealed;
- in case of fire or natural disasters;
- before drawing up the liquidation balance when the enterprise is being liquidated and in other cases.

According to the scope of the inspection, the inventory can be divided into general or selective, scheduled or sudden inventories.

The head of the enterprise and the chief accountant lead the inventory transfer. The inventory of production stocks is carried out by the inventorying working commissions with the participation of the materially responsible person.

During the inventory period, the availability of material assets is determined by weighing, measuring, and counting methods and formalized in the list. The list is signed by the financially responsible person.

As a result of the inventory, the difference between the information in the material documents and the actual balance is formalized in the reconciliation report.

Differences between the actual existing property and the accounting information determined as a result of the inventory of production stocks are reflected as follows:

a) Due to the fact that a deficit of 50,000 soums has been identified in terms of materials and the person responsible for the deficit has not been found, the amount of the deficit will be transferred to the expenses of the period:

As a result of the inventory, a deficit was found:

Dt 5910-"Loss due to deficits and impairment of value" - 50,000 soums

Kt 1010-"Raw materials and materials" school - 50,000 soums.

The amount of the deficit was transferred to the expenses of the period:

Dt 9430-"Other operating expenses" - 50,000 soums

Certificate 5910-"Deficits and losses due to impairment" - 50,000 soums.

In accordance with paragraph 3 of the "Regulation on the procedure for reflecting deficits and surpluses in accounting" during the inventory, the market value of the property in which the deficit was determined can be determined as follows:

a) on the basis of written information of the producer or his dealer, commodity exchanges about the prices of similar property;

b) on the basis of information on the level of evaluation available in the relevant state bodies;

c) based on the grade levels published in mass media and special literature during the inventory;

g) based on the expert opinion of the appraiser about the value of the relevant property.

Determining the amount of damage caused to the employer's property, determining the procedure for recovery from the employee is regulated by the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The procedure for recovery of material damages in the amount not exceeding the average salary of the employee is determined on the basis of the order of the management of the enterprise. The order of the head of the enterprise must be issued within one month from the date of detection of material damage. In this case, damages should be assessed at market rates.

If the amount of material damage exceeds the employee's average monthly salary or more than one month has passed since the date of determination, the collection of material damage shall be carried out through the court.

If the person (or other persons) materially responsible for the amount of the identified deficit is found guilty, and the market value of the property for which the deficit is identified is higher than its balance sheet value, it is reflected in the accounting records as follows:

As a result of the inventory, a shortage was found;

ДТ 5910-"Losses due to deficits and impairment of values"

Кт 1010-"Raw materials and materials" school

The amount to be deducted from the financially responsible person:

Дт 4730-"Debt of employees for compensation of material damages" school

КТ 5910-"Deficits and losses due to impairment of values" scho'ti

30,000 soums were determined as income from recovery of deficits on material assets

ДТ 5910-"Deficits and losses due to impairment of values" school

Кт 9390-"Other operating income" school

The natural reduction of production reserves within the limits of the norms approved by law is transferred to the production costs according to the instructions of the head of the enterprise.

According to the "Regulation on the procedure for reflecting deficits and surpluses in accounting" as a result of the inventory, if a deficit or surplus of properties is found, it will be taxed in the manner established by the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

If, as a result of the inventory of inventory, it is determined that there is excess property, it is included in the financial results:

Д -т 1010-"Raw materials and materials" school

Кт 9390-"Other operating income" school.

Summary.

The main purpose of inventory of production stocks is to determine the actual availability of assets and to compare these data with accounting data. As a result of the conducted inventory, inventory differences can be determined in the form of surplus or deficit of production stocks. The reasons for this may be errors in accounting and incorrect calculations, natural depletion of production reserves, various natural disasters (fires, floods, etc.), as well as the actions of enterprise employees (guilty or innocent). . Therefore, upon completion of the inventory, all collected materials must be submitted to the accounting department in order to make corrections to the differences between the inventory documents and the data of the accounting documents.

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